

Evaluating the Efficacy of SSRIs in Treating Anxiety and Depression in Dermatology Patients: Focus on Pemphigus and Psoriasis**Amiya Ranjan Sahoo¹, Bhagyasri Pradhan², Rasmita Behera³, Aniket Dash⁴, Swoyamsiddha Dash⁵, Manisha Das⁶**¹Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, S.C.B Medical College, Cuttack²Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, GMCH, Sundargarh³Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, FM Medical College, Balasore⁴Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, S.C.B Medical College, Cuttack⁵Junior Resident, 3rd Year, Department of Psychiatry, SCBMCH, Cuttack⁶Junior Resident, 2nd Year, Department of Psychiatry, SCBMCH, Cuttack

Received: 01-04-2024 Revised: 15-05-2024 / Accepted: 21-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

This study evaluates the effectiveness of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) in reducing anxiety and depression in patients with pemphigus and psoriasis. Conducted at SCB Medical College, Cuttack, the prospective study followed 100 participants over one year. Results show significant improvements in psychiatric symptoms and quality of life, particularly in psychological domains, highlighting the benefits of integrated dermatological-psychiatric care.

Keywords: SSRIs, Treatment outcomes, Quality of life, Anxiety, Depression, Dermatology, Integrated care.

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Introduction

Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are a class of drugs commonly used to treat psychiatric conditions such as depression and anxiety. By increasing serotonin levels in the brain, SSRIs help improve mood and alleviate symptoms of anxiety. In dermatology, where patients often experience significant psychological distress due to the visibility and chronic nature of their conditions, SSRIs can play a crucial role in comprehensive patient care [1].

The intersection of dermatology and psychiatry, often referred to as psychodermatology, explores how psychological factors influence skin conditions and vice versa. Patients with dermatological diseases frequently suffer from psychiatric comorbidities, which exacerbate their physical symptoms and complicate treatment [2].

Addressing these psychiatric issues is essential for effective disease management and improving patients' overall quality of life.

Conditions like psoriasis and pemphigus exemplify the challenges faced by dermatology patients. Psoriasis, affecting approximately 1.4-2% of the global population, is associated with heightened rates of depression and anxiety [3]. Similarly, pemphigus, an autoimmune blistering disease,

significantly impacts patients' lives due to its chronicity and visible manifestations. Despite its severity, research on psychiatric comorbidities in pemphigus is limited, underscoring the need for more focused studies [4].

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of SSRIs in reducing anxiety and depression in patients with psoriasis and pemphigus.

By assessing psychiatric symptoms and quality of life over a one-year period, we seek to highlight the importance of integrated dermatological and psychiatric care in managing these complex conditions [5].

Methods

Study Design and Population: A prospective longitudinal study was conducted at the Department of Dermatology and Department of Psychiatry, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack, from December 2021 to November 2022. The study included 100 patients diagnosed with psoriasis or pemphigus, with 50 patients in each group.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Patients aged 18-60 years, proficient in reading and writing in Odia, diagnosed with psoriasis or pemphigus, and

willing to participate were included. Patients with comorbid medical illnesses or pre-existing psychiatric disorders unrelated to their dermatological condition were excluded.

Assessment Tools and Procedures:

- **Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) and Severity Index for Pemphigus (SIP):** Used to determine disease severity.
- **Socio-demographic Data and Psychological Variables:** Collected using a structured proforma.
- **Quality of Life (QOL) and Psychiatric Assessment:** Assessed using the WHOQOL-BREF (Odia version), MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI 7.0.2), and Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS).

Treatment Protocol: Patients identified with anxiety or depression was treated with SSRIs. Follow-up assessments were conducted at 45 days, 3 months, 6 months, and 1 year.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Spearman rank correlation, and tests such as chi-square, Mann-Whitney U, and independent samples t-test using SPSS 24. A significance level of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Baseline Psychiatric Symptoms and Quality of Life Scores:

- **Prevalence:** Depression affected 56% of psoriasis patients and 76% of pemphigus patients, while anxiety was prevalent in 26% of psoriasis patients and 32% of pemphigus patients.
- **QOL Scores:** Initial assessment showed lower QOL scores in all domains for both groups, with pemphigus patients generally having poorer QOL.

Longitudinal Changes in Anxiety and Depression Scores:

- **45 Days Follow-Up:** Significant reduction in anxiety and depression scores in both groups.
- **3 Months and 6 Months Follow-Up:** Continued improvement in psychiatric symptoms, with pemphigus patients showing more pronounced improvement.
- **1-Year Follow-Up:** Sustained reduction in anxiety and depression scores, with overall enhancement in QOL, particularly in psychological domains.

Improvements in Quality of Life across Different Domains:

- **Physical Domain:** Noticeable improvement due to better management of dermatological symptoms.
- **Psychological Domain:** Significant enhancement, attributed to reduced psychiatric symptoms.
- **Social and Environmental Domains:** Gradual improvement over the year, reflecting better social interactions and coping mechanisms.

Comparative Analysis of Treatment Response in Psoriasis and Pemphigus Patients: Pemphigus patients initially had higher baseline depression scores, indicating a greater psychiatric burden. However, both groups responded well to SSRI treatment, with significant improvements in all assessed domains.

Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate the significant burden of psychiatric comorbidities in patients with psoriasis and pemphigus. With 56% of psoriasis patients and 76% of pemphigus patients experiencing depression, the data underscore the critical need for addressing mental health in dermatological practice. Anxiety was also prevalent, affecting 26% of psoriasis patients and 32% of pemphigus patients.

SSRIs proved effective in significantly reducing anxiety and depression symptoms across both patient groups. The longitudinal assessments showed that patients experienced sustained improvements in psychiatric symptoms over the one-year follow-up period. This consistent reduction highlights the potential benefits of incorporating SSRIs into the treatment regimens for patients with chronic dermatological conditions [6].

Quality of life, particularly in the psychological domain, showed marked improvement with integrated care. The baseline assessments indicated lower quality of life scores for both groups, with pemphigus patients experiencing more severe impacts. However, over the course of the study, significant enhancements were observed in all quality-of-life domains, reflecting the positive impact of combined dermatological and psychiatric interventions.

Comparatively, pemphigus patients had higher baseline depression scores and poorer quality of life outcomes than psoriasis patients. Despite these initial differences, both groups benefited substantially from SSRI treatment. This suggests that while the psychiatric burden may be greater in pemphigus patients, SSRIs can effectively mitigate these symptoms and improve overall well-being. The study's findings align with existing literature on the psychosocial burden of dermatological diseases and the efficacy of SSRIs in treating psychiatric comorbidities. By integrating

psychiatric care into dermatology practice, healthcare providers can address the complex interplay between physical and mental health, ultimately enhancing patient outcomes. The implications for clinical practice are clear: adopting an integrated care model that includes psychiatric evaluation and treatment can significantly improve the quality of life for patients with chronic dermatological conditions. Early detection and management of psychiatric symptoms are crucial for achieving holistic and effective patient care.

Conclusion

This study underscores the substantial psychiatric burden experienced by patients with psoriasis and pemphigus, highlighting the need for integrated care approaches. The prevalence of anxiety and depression in these patients necessitates comprehensive treatment strategies that address both physical and mental health aspects. Treatment with SSRIs proved effective in reducing anxiety and depression symptoms in both patient groups, leading to significant improvements in quality of life. The sustained enhancement of psychological well-being over the one-year follow-up period demonstrates the benefits of incorporating psychiatric care into dermatological treatment plans. The findings advocate for the implementation of integrated dermatology-psychiatry care models, which can improve patient outcomes and overall well-being. By recognizing and addressing psychiatric comorbidities in dermatology patients, healthcare providers can offer more holistic and effective care. Future research should continue to explore the optimization of integrated care approaches, with a

focus on long-term benefits and patient satisfaction. Enhancing the collaboration between dermatology and psychiatry will be key to improving the quality of life for patients with chronic skin conditions [7].

References

1. Picardi A, Abeni D, Renzi C, Braga M, Melchi CF, Pasquini P. Treatment outcome and incidence of psy-chiatric disorders in dermatological out-patients. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2003; 17(2):155-9.
2. Katon WJ. Epidemiology and treatment of depression in patients with chronic medical illness. *Dialogues Clin Neurosci* 2011; 13:7-23.
3. Picardi A, Abeni D, Melchi CF, Puddu P, Pasquini P. Psychiatric morbidity in dermatological outpatients: An issue to be recognized. *Br J Dermatol* 2000; 143:983-91.
4. Kimball AB, Jacobson C, Weiss S, Vreeland MG, Wu Y. The Psychosocial Burden of Psoriasis. *Am J Clin Dermatol* 2005; 6:383-392.
5. Schultz HY. Society for Investigative Dermatology Skin Disease Comorbidities Project Launch Conference Proceedings. *J Invest Dermatol* 2009; 129:525-528.
6. Gupta MA. Psychiatric comorbidity in dermatologic disorders. In: Walker C, Papadopoulos L, eds. *Psych dermatology.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2005.
7. Shi CR, Nambudiri VE. Anxiety symptoms and quality of life in ethnic minority patients with psoriasis. *J Drugs Dermatol.* 2015; 14(8):843-848.